

Solar Energy Conversion and Storage : An Overview

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One of the most important and vital requirements of the modern society is energy since the ancient period. Consumption of energy is regularly increasing on one hand whereas the natural resources are depleted at an ever increasing pace on the other. The estimates are frightening, that the major energy resources like petrol, gas, kerosene etc. are likely to be exhausted somewhere in the coming century. This is supported by a continuous and steep rise in oil prices by many folds. The combustion of fossil fuels is giving rise to environmental pollution. The increasing amount of carbon dioxide in atmosphere has reached an alarming situation, thus causing the global warming.

Nature is utilising the carbon dioxide of the atmosphere to form carbohydrates by the well known process of photosynthesis and only a little amount of solar input (0.023%) is utilised. This negligibly small part of the solar energy is utilised for feeding the whole world. On these grounds, solar energy must be appreciated as an alternate source of energy in future and it must be harnessed for the development and the human welfare of the mankind. It is utmost necessary to search for alternate sources of energy to fulfil the energy demands of the modern society for today and tomorrow. Here solar energy and photoreduction of carbon dioxide enters the scene. Although, solar energy is harmless, low cost, abundantly available, inexhaustible and a new source of energy but it is also associated with some problems, like lower radiation flux, daily and seasonal fluctuations and a limited photoperiod.

Photosynthesis is a well established natural process and efforts should be made to mimick such a reaction under laboratory conditions. This will not only help in solving the problem of energy resources but it will also put a check on increasing amount of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere.

Photogeneration of electricity : The photoelectrochemical production of electricity has attracted the attention of many scientists as a viable media for solar energy conversion with a bright future prospects. The photoeffects in electrochemical systems were first reported by Becquerel^{1,2} in his investigations on the solar illumination of metal electrodes long back. Later, Moser³ and Rigolot⁴ noticed an increase in photocurrent when Ag/AgCl and Cu/CuO electrodes were coated with a dye and exposed to light. Similar observations were reported by Thompson⁵, Stora⁶ and Potter and Thaller⁷ in case of metal electrodes immersed in dye solution or coated with dye. Earlier observations on photopotential were mainly characterised by a change in the direction of polarity of the e.m.f. measured during irradiation. Lavine *et al.*⁸⁻¹⁰ attempted to correlate these photopotentials with the fluorescence properties of different organic compounds. Surash and Hercules¹¹ proved that only negative photopotential should be obtained with carbonyl compounds.

At that time, this effect was called 'Becquerel effect'. It is now known as 'photoelectrochemical effect', and is defined as the change in the electrode potential (in open-circuit) or in the current flowing (in closed-circuit) on irradiation of an electrode/electrolyte system. This change in the potential or the current may be due to some photochemical reactions in the solution generating electroactive products. This field gained a momentum with the reports of Fujishima and Honda¹² and has been excellently reviewed by Kuwana¹³, Archer¹⁴, Nozik¹⁵, Harries and Wilson¹⁶, Rajeshwar *et al.*¹⁷, Tomkiewicz and Fay¹⁸, Butler and Ginley¹⁹, Aruchamy *et al.*²⁰, Holmstrom²¹, Guay *et al.*²² and Ameta *et al.*²³.

Semiconductor based photoelectrochemical cells offer a simple and efficient method for direct conversion of light into electricity. The optical to electrical conversion efficiency (η) as high as 12% have been realised in these cells, however, the theoretically attainable efficiency is 20–30%²⁰.

The major problem associated with the use of semiconductors in photoelectrochemical cells is the photocorrosion of semiconductor electrodes. This photocorrosion may be controlled by judicious choice of all the three compounds of the cell, the electrode material, the electrolyte and the redox couple. Gerischer²⁴ used the redox couple ferrocyanide/ferricyanide with CdS electrode to protect it from photocorrosion. Later, Miller and Heller²⁵, Hodes *et al.*²⁶ and Ellis *et al.*²⁷ used S_x^{n-} system to put a check on photocorrosion of electrodes, however, the use of polysulphide electrolytes raised some other problems, like their yellow colour, toxicity and air-sensitivity.

Naufi *et al.*²⁸ used methanolic solution of tetramethylammonium hexacyanoferrate as an electrolyte and the cell worked for 700 h without loss of photocurrent and the degradation of the electrode n-CdSe. Recently, corrosion of semiconductor was reported by Arce and Ibanez²⁹ and Carlsson *et al.*³⁰. Some non-aqueous solvents were also used successfully in photoelectrochemical cells by Nakatani and Tsubomura³¹, White *et al.*³², Nakato *et al.*³³ and Nagasubramanian *et al.*³⁴. Some inorganic electrolytes like liquid ammonia and a molten salt electrolyte (1 : 1 mixture of AlCl₃ and butylpyridinium chloride) have been used by Malpas *et al.*³⁵ and Singh *et al.*³⁶, respectively.

Ang and Sammells^{37–39} used platinum and molybdenum selenide as cathode and photoanode respectively, using the two redox couples Br⁻/Br₂ and I⁻/I₂ in the two halves of the cells. Use of tetraphenylporphyrins coated n-SnO₂ electrode was reported by Tien and Higgins⁴⁰ whereas Itoh *et al.*⁴¹ used rhodamine-B sensitised electrodes in photoelectrochemical cell. Alonso *et al.*⁴² reported the use of electrodeposited CdSe_{0.5}Te_{0.5} electrode for solar energy conversion whereas chlorophyll sensitised TiO₂ electrodes were used by Kamat *et al.*⁴³.

An improvement in conversion efficiency to 11.5% has been reported by Heller *et al.*⁴⁴. Nair *et al.*⁴⁵ used chemically deposited CuS thin film whereas Khare⁴⁶ used CdS as an electrode. Some conducting polymers like thin polypyrrole-films are

coated on metal⁴⁷ and semiconductor electrodes^{48,49} and it was observed that photodegradation of these coated electrodes was controlled to some extent and these are relatively more stable than the uncoated ones. However, peeling off of the film was reported in aqueous solutions. Some polypyrrole clay modified electrodes were used recently by Rudzinski *et al.*⁵⁰.

The efficiency of the photoelectrochemical cells can be improved by chemical etching of the surface of the photoanode. Parkinson *et al.*⁵¹ reported 60% increase in the short circuit current with gallium arsenide electrode in polyselenide electrolyte without affecting the fill factor and open-circuit voltage, whereas Heller *et al.*^{52,53} reported an improvement in the efficiency from 0.003% to 7.5% by chemical etching of a single crystal CdSe electrode. The effect of photoelectrochemical etching was also reported by Tenne and Hodes⁵⁴, Liu *et al.*⁵⁵ and Tenne^{56,57}. Recently, mirage effect has been reported by Decker and Fracastor-Decker⁵⁸, whereas photoelectric conversion with dye multilayers on a semiconductor electrode was investigated by Sato *et al.*⁵⁹. Mandal *et al.*⁶⁰ reported the photoelectrochemical effect with a surface modified n-CdTe electrode while enhancement of photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ was reported by Anpo⁶¹.

Recently, Tennakone *et al.*⁶² have reported an interesting stable dye-sensitised photoelectrochemical cell. Rideal and Williams⁶³ discovered the photogalvanic effect in 1925 but it was systematically studied by Rabinowitch^{64,65}. Later, Kaneko and Yamada⁶⁶, Fox and Kabir-ud-din⁶⁷, Murthy *et al.*^{68–70}, Daul *et al.*⁷¹, Perrone *et al.*⁷², Rohatgi-Mukherjee *et al.*⁷³, Ameta *et al.*^{74–77} and Aliwi and Hanna⁷⁸ reported some interesting photogalvanic systems. Ameta *et al.*⁷⁹ also reported a newer approach to solar energy conversion involving some thermoelectrochemical cells.

Photogeneration of hydrogen : Photodecomposition reactions are considered of much importance, because energy-rich photoproducts will prove to be the fuel of future. The gaseous photoproducts have proved more promising as these can be stored easily and transported conveniently. However, due to higher entropy of gases, there may be some loss of energy. The photodissociation of water in natural photosynthesis is an endothermic reaction and 284 kJ mol⁻¹ energy is released during

splitting of H_2O into its constituents $\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ and $\text{O}_2(\text{g})$,

This reaction involves two half reactions : (1) reductive step, in which hydrogen is formed (involving two electrons) and (ii) an oxidative step, producing oxygen (involvement of four electrons). The energy required for the dissociation of water, thus depends on the number of electrons involved in this redox process,

The conduction band of the semiconductor used for photolysis must be at a more negative potential than redox potential for the reaction (2) leading to reduction of water and the valence band must be at a more positive potential than the redox potential for the reaction (3) for the corresponding oxidation of water. The band gap of a semiconductor necessary for photolysis of water should be 1.23 eV, but factors like overpotential, loss of energy, etc. make the semiconductor with large band gap (2.1 eV) more suitable for this process.

Fujishima and Honda⁸⁰ were the first to report the photoelectrolysis of water using TiO_2 as semiconductor, however, the evolution of oxygen at illuminated TiO_2 electrode-electrolyte interface was observed by Boddy⁸¹ earlier. TiO_2 has been found more stable against photocorrosion during this process than other semiconductors. Bard and Wrighton⁸² reported the direct photolysis of water using an external bias voltage. Yoneyama *et al.*⁸³ and Wrighton *et al.*⁸⁴ used strontium titanate whereas RuO_2 and CdS catalysed hydrogen generation from water was studied by Amouyal *et al.*⁸⁵ and Darwent and Porter⁸⁶ respectively. Kuznetov *et al.*⁸⁷ and Hodes *et al.*⁸⁸ used HfO_2 and WO_3 photoanodes whereas barium titanate was used by Nasby and Quinn⁸⁹.

Some sensitised semiconductor electrodes were reported by Spitler and Calvin⁹⁰, Fujihira *et al.*⁹¹, Memming *et al.*⁹² and Dare Edwards *et al.*⁹³. Recently, activation of photoelectrodes by heteropolyanions for hydrogen generation was

studied by Kaito and Nadjo^{94,95}. A very interesting system for photolysis of water involving use of RuO_2 and TiO_2 with attached platinum particles, was reported by Kiwi and Gratzel^{96,97} and Kiwi *et al.*⁹⁸, whereas Prasad *et al.*⁹⁹ reported hydrogen production on TiO_2 and WSe_2 photoelectrodes. Taqui Khan *et al.*¹⁰⁰ used $\text{TiO}_2\text{-Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}$ -ascorbic acid system. The use of proflavin- $\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}$ -triethanolamine- K_2PtCl_6 system for the generation of hydrogen was reported by Oncescu *et al.*¹⁰¹, while John *et al.*¹⁰² were able to evolve hydrogen by photocatalytic oxidation of glucose on platinised TiO_2 powder. Some xanthene dyes have been reported to act as antenna molecule for the photoreduction of water^{102,103}.

Tennakone *et al.*¹⁰⁴ were able to liberate hydrogen with the oxidation of trichlorocuprate(I) ions to trichlorocuprate(II). The evolution of molecular hydrogen during the atmospheric oxidation of coal has been reported by Davidi and Cohen¹⁰⁵ whereas Vilchis and Vong¹⁰⁶ and Sobczynski¹⁰⁷ used respectively samarium hydroxide and molybdenum disulphide as catalyst for hydrogen evolution.

During the photocatalysis of oligo(*para*-phenylenes), the photoreductive production of hydrogen and ethanol in aqueous triethylamine was reported by Matsuoka *et al.*¹⁰⁸. Zhang and Baerns¹⁰⁹ used cerium dioxide as catalyst for hydrogen formation by steam reforming and water-gas shift reaction in the oxidative methane coupling reaction. The solar energy conversion from photolysis of water by biological and chemical systems were reviewed by Delarosa *et al.*¹¹⁰.

Recently, Medyantseva and Budnikov¹¹¹ were able to release hydrogen catalytically at graphite and carbon paste electrodes in solution of complexes of lead(II) and cadmium(II) with sulphur containing ligands. Mills¹¹² used platinum group metals in the decomposition of water. The photolysis of tetrahydroxostannate(II) ions in aqueous media for hydrogen evolution was studied by Tennakone and Ketipearachchi¹¹³. They reported the formation of hexahydroxostannate(IV) as the product. A new hydrogen storage material TiFeCr/NaM was reported by Xu *et al.*¹¹⁴.

Photoproduction of energy rich system : The photochemical production of energy rich compounds has attained a considerable interest

during the last two decades. The production of strong oxidants is considered to be an alternate way to store solar energy. In this context, the formation of bromide ion from bromine by a charge transfer from ligand to metal in FeBr^{2+} complex ion has been studied by Chen *et al.*¹¹⁵,

Scharf and Weitz¹¹⁶ reported the formation of the chlorine from aqueous HCl, which is an endergonic reaction. It involves the oxidation of HCl by oxygen in the presence of sodium anthraquinone-2-sulphonate as the catalyst,

This reaction may be compared with the oxidation of HCl in gaseous phase using cuprous chloride as catalyst. Luther and Weigert¹¹⁷ reported the dimerisation of anthracene, which is a first ever studied organic photoreduction from solar energy storage point of view. The photoisomerisation of norbornadiene to quadricyclane¹¹⁸ and 1-ethoxy-carbonyl-1-*H*-azepine^{119,120} are other prospective systems. Later on, it was observed that the dimer of methoxynaphthalene are too reactive for storage. However, their capability to store solar energy (per unit weight) is more^{121,122}.

Usai *et al.*¹²³ reported the dye-sensitised photochemical production of hydrogen peroxide in the eosine/ O_2 /EDTA system. Mukai and Yamashita¹²⁴, Hamada *et al.*¹²⁵, Maruyama *et al.*¹²⁶ and Mehta and Shrikrishna^{121,122} reported some promising systems involving the conversion of a secocage molecule into a cage compound on irradiation. The cage structure stored the energy in the form of chemical strain and can release it back as thermal energy either on heating or in the presence of some specific catalysts. Although the concept seems to be quite simple but much more experimental work is required to see that such systems will prove to be commercially useful.

The hydrogen atom abstraction reactions are also of importance. The hydrogen atom generated from splitting of H-OH bond in a photodissociation step can be used either to form hydrogen or to react with another molecules (e.g. carbon dioxide) to yield alternative energy rich molecules (e.g. formaldehyde),

Therefore, such reactions might be a more feasible way of storing energy than actually producing molecular hydrogen.

Photosynthesis is still an existing challenge for photochemists. In this direction, the photoreduction of carbon dioxide and related compounds has been investigated by many workers¹²⁷⁻¹³⁴. Recently, Yamamura *et al.*¹³⁵, Aliwi and Al-Jubori¹³⁶, Taqui Khan *et al.*¹³⁷, Ogura *et al.*¹³⁸ and Ameta *et al.*^{139,140} were able to produce energy-rich products from the photoreduction of carbon dioxide. The photoreduction of nitrogen or related compounds to energetic products like ammonia and hydrazine has also been carried out by Denisov *et al.*¹⁴¹, Didenko *et al.*¹⁴², Nikonova *et al.*¹⁴³, Taqui Khan *et al.*¹⁴⁴, Kudo *et al.*¹⁴⁵ and Tennakone *et al.*^{146,147}.

Photocatalytic conversion of solar energy : Total photosynthetic production of energy on the earth, in terms of carbon is estimated to be 2×10^{11} tons/year¹⁴⁸, which is approximately 10 times the total energy demand of the mankind. The green plants and some bacteria utilise as little as 0.023% of the total solar energy reaching on the earth through natural photosynthesis. Many attempts of chemical conversion have been made under the heading 'artificial photosynthesis'. These include mainly the decomposition of water, reduction of carbon dioxide and nitrogen fixation, etc. In nature, water, carbon dioxide and nitrogen are activated to produce energy-rich compounds through photosynthetic processes. The energy contained in these products is released again to maintain the life cycle in one or the other manner.

The photodecomposition of water (which exists inexhaustably on the earth) produces a sound energy system, that is, hydrogen. The reduction of carbon dioxide would enable us to synthesise various organic compounds. Nitrogen fixation under mild conditions would be an important means of producing nitrogen containing compounds.

To induce these redox reactions, a photocatalyst or a photosensitiser like chlorophyll is required in natural photosynthesis. Various photocatalysts were used involving dye molecules and complexes such as $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ in homogeneous systems, some chalcogenides and ternary semiconductors in a heterogeneous systems, etc.

Fujishima and Honda⁸⁰ were able to decompose water using TiO₂ as photocatalyst. Yoneyama *et al.*⁸³ used strontium titanate whereas Nasby and Quinn⁸⁹ used barium titanate for splitting water to produce hydrogen. Some sensitised semiconductor electrodes were also used by many workers⁹⁰⁻⁹³ whereas Kawai and Sakata¹⁴⁸, Domen *et al.*¹⁴⁹, Lehn *et al.*¹⁵⁰ have enhanced photolysis of water by using metal or metal oxide supported on semiconductor surfaces.

Kawai and Sakata¹⁵¹⁻¹⁵⁴ investigated the hydrogen production from the photocatalytic reduction of water and organic compounds. They observed the reaction of solid carbon with water to produce hydrogen under ambient conditions. The temperature requirement for this water-gas reaction is more than 800° but with the use of TiO₂ as a photocatalyst and in presence of light, it is possible to drive this reaction even at room temperature,

Similarly, the photocatalytic reactions of alcohol and water produce hydrogen vigorously^{153,154}. In case of ethanol, methane, carbon dioxide and hydrogen were produced. There seems to be some side-reactions in addition to this reaction,

Carbon dioxide is an extremely abundant, inexpensive and indirect resource of energy, because it is a waste product of many industries such as limestone and cement, fermentation of carbohydrates, and on a vast scale in fossil-burning power plants. The photochemical reactions of carbon dioxide are of much interest and attracted the attention of many chemists. Photocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide has been studied by Getoff^{127,155}, Inoue *et al.*¹⁵⁶, Aurian-Blajeni *et al.*¹²⁸, Stalder *et al.*¹³⁰, Chen *et al.*¹⁵⁷ and Ameta *et al.*^{139,140} using a series of semiconducting materials such as TiO₂, ZnO, CdS, GaP and SiC suspended in aqueous solution as photocatalysts and they were able to produce energy-rich products like formic

acid, formaldehyde, methanol and sometimes even traces of methane,

The reaction between carbon dioxide and water to form organic compounds like formic acid, formaldehyde, methanol and methane involves 2,4,6- and 8-electron transfers. Hemminger *et al.*¹⁵⁸ reported that this reaction requires a smaller energy input per electron transferred than required for water splitting and has also been proposed as a convenient storage material¹⁵⁹.

The photoassisted reduction of carbon dioxide on semiconductor powder using either aqueous suspension and coated surfaces of these materials were also investigated by Halmann and Aurian-Blajeni¹⁶⁰. The first electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide to formic acid was reported more than a century ago by Royer¹⁶¹. This work was reviewed by Russel *et al.*¹⁶². Recently, Aloguchi *et al.*¹⁶³, Furuya and Koide¹⁶⁴ and Nakato *et al.*¹⁶⁵ studied the electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide using different metal electrodes. Recently, photocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide to methane and acetic acid has been reported by Ishitani *et al.*¹⁶⁶.

Selective photoreduction of carbon dioxide in aqueous titania mixed with Cu-powder has been reported by Hirano *et al.*¹⁶⁷ while Kanemoto *et al.*¹⁶⁸ reported the photoreduction of CO₂ catalysed by ZnS. Recently, photocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide in presence of dye-sensitised titania powder was observed by Ameta *et al.*¹⁶⁹.

Photosynthetic products like carbohydrates, fats and proteins are also good sources of hydrogen production. These products are oxidised to produce hydrogen, thus reducing water at the same time.

Norris *et al.*¹⁷⁰ and Kawai and Sakata¹⁹¹ reported the production of hydrogen from carbohydrates (i.e. glucose, sugar, starch, cellulose, etc.).

On comparing the natural photosynthesis through which light energy is stored, with the photocatalytic reaction, in which hydrogen is produced from glucose and water, it may be concluded that photocatalytic reaction is isoenergetic with the photosynthesis reaction,

Various other biomasses, like amino acids^{172,173} and proteins (the nitrogen containing compounds) are decomposed with water in presence of photocatalysts, where ammonia as well as hydrogen are produced.

Some artificial polymers¹⁷², like nylon, PVC, polyethylene, urea resin, etc. and organic acids were also reported as a source of hydrogen. The photocatalytic reduction of nitrogen to ammonia is of immense interest as it offers an alternate and low energy route to the energy intensive Haber-Bosch synthesis of ammonia at high temperature and pressure.

Volpin and Shur¹⁷⁴ were the first to reduce the molecular nitrogen in solution using transition metal complexes whereas reduction of nitrogen with metal compounds was developed by Allen and Senoff¹⁷⁵. Shilov *et al.*¹⁷⁶ reported intermediate nitrogen complexes which can further convert nitrogen into hydrazine and ammonia derivatives. The first system for nitrogen reduction in protic media to produce hydrazine and ammonia was reported by Denisov *et al.*^{177,178}, which is close in its mechanism to the enzymatic nitrogen fixation.

Although hydroxides^{179,180} of some metals like Ti^{III}, Cr^{II}, etc. reduce the molecular nitrogen at a considerable rate, but the yield of the reduced products was found to be quite low. This might be increased by the presence of metal dopants^{181,182} like Mo, Fe, Co, Ni, etc. These dopants also cause conversion of the anatase form of TiO₂ to the rutile.

A multielectron reducing agent with sufficiently low negative redox potential is required

to reduce nitrogen in protic media. This condition may be achieved at cathode in electrochemical nitrogen reduction. It is necessary to use such materials for the cathode, which can have a considerable overvoltage to prevent hydrogen evolution at negative cathode potential. At cathode, ions of alkali metals are discharged to produce amalgam, which becomes a real reducing agent of N₂. Addition of sodium amalgam to the nitrogen fixing system Ti(OH)₃-Mo^{III}¹⁸³ increases the activity towards nitrogen reduction and the yield of the reduced products also.

Didenko *et al.*¹⁸⁴ reported the non-biological catalytic reduction of molecular nitrogen at room temperature using Mo^{III} complex containing Mg^{II} ions as catalyst whereas the dependence of the yield of hydrazine and ammonia on current density in electrocatalytic reduction of nitrogen was reported by Gorodyskii *et al.*¹⁸⁵. Nikonova *et al.*¹⁸⁶ reduced the nitrogen to ammonia in homogeneous aqueous and alcoholic solution of V^{II} complexes with catechol, even at room temperature and atmospheric nitrogen pressure. Thus the overall process of nitrogen fixation is recognised to constitute two main events : (i) binding of nitrogen molecule to a metal ion at ambient conditions and (ii) the reduction/oxidation of coordinated nitrogen to ammonia.

Schrauzer and Guth¹⁸⁷ reported the reduction of molecular nitrogen on illuminated TiO₂ surfaces to produce ammonia and hydrazine.

Radford and Francis¹⁸⁸ were able to reduce nitrogen in aqueous suspensions. Photocatalytic production of ammonia over CdS-Pt-RuO₂ and Pt-TiO₂ has been investigated by Taqui Khan *et al.*¹⁴⁴ and Kudo *et al.*¹⁴⁵ respectively. Tennakone *et al.*¹⁴⁶ used hydrous cuprous oxide to photoreduce nitrogen to ammonia while the protonation of bridging dinitrogen to yield ammonia were reported by Leigh *et al.*¹⁸⁹.

Recently, Tennakone *et al.*^{190,191} used some hydrous oxides of samarium(III) and europium(III) and ultrafine particles of Fe(O)OH for the photoreduction of nitrogen in aqueous medium; whereas Ileperuma *et al.*¹⁹² reported the

photoreduction of nitrogen and water on montmorillonite clays loaded with hydrated ferrous oxide.

Although the field of photocatalysis has a little span of two decades and a number of workers have investigated the photocatalytic reactions of synthetic and mechanistic importance but still this field is in its infant stage as far as the application part is concerned. One of the most important applications of photocatalysis is to generate high energy products, which can be used as fuels. Photolysis of water, photoreduction of nitrogen and carbon dioxide, photogeneration of halogens from halides, etc. carried out under photocatalytic conditions provide promising areas, where a break-through is possible in coming years. Thus, such reactions will help the world in getting relieved from the cancerous grip of energy crisis.

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